

Communication Patterns and Leadership Styles of Administrators as Correlates of Organizational Climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study investigated communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria. Five research questions guided the study and five null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 749 administrators in public universities in South East, Nigeria. A sample size of 300 administrators was drawn for the study using proportionate stratified sampling techniques. A researcher developed questionnaires titled “Communication Patterns Questionnaire (CPQ)”, “Leadership Styles Questionnaire (LSQ)” and “Organizational Climate Scale (QCS)” were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from the Department of Educational Foundations, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistency of the instruments which yielded overall co-efficient values of 0.80, 0.82 and 0.82 for CPQ, LSQ and OCS respectively. The researcher together with four research assistants collected data for the study using the direct approach method and 97% return was recorded. Pearson Product Moment Correlational Coefficient was used to answer the research questions 1-4 and t-test of correlation to test hypotheses 1-4, while multiple regression was used to answer research question 5 and test hypothesis 5. The findings of the study revealed among others that downward and horizontal communication patterns of administrators have strong positive relationship with organization climate. Further results indicted that democratic leadership style of administrators has strong positive relationship with organizational climate in public universities South East, Nigeria. It was also revealed that all dimensions of communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators have significant relationship with organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that university management should organize training programmes in forms of annually or quarterly conferences, seminars, short-courses and workshops to enable administrators acquire skills and knowledge of applying communication patterns and leadership styles to create positive organizational climate.

Key words: Communication Patterns, Leadership styles, Downward, Horizontal, Administrators, Organizational Climate

Introduction

Higher education is the post secondary level of education that enables individuals to gain knowledge and acquire skills to improve their sources of livelihood and also contribute to the development of the society. It also inculcates sound moral values and character that promotes peaceful coexistence of individuals in the society. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) noted that higher education is the education given after post basic education in institutions such as Colleges of Education, Monotechnics, Polytechnics, Universities and other specialized institutions such as Colleges of Agriculture, School of Health and Technology and the National Teachers' Institutes (NTI). The focus of this study is on university.

University is an institution of higher learning where people study to acquire knowledge, shape their character and obtain degrees in different disciplines. Tofi, Agada and Okafor (2020) opined that university is the foremost tertiary institution in Nigeria with responsibility for equipping people with knowledge and skills to undertake tasks and employment functions which are necessary for transformation of societies. The authors added that the functions of university in Nigeria include: teaching, research, production of texts, certification, storage and retrieval of knowledge, community service and enlightenment service. Universities offer opportunity for people to study at an undergraduate level for first degrees and at postgraduate level for advanced degrees. Similarly, Asuquo and Ekpoh (2020) opined that as the apex of education, every university is expected to generate knowledge, ideas, skills and disseminate same through teaching, learning, research and community services.

There are public and private universities in Nigeria which are regulated by National Universities Commission. The focus of the study is on the public universities which are established, financed and managed by State or Federal Government. Akpakwu and Okwo (2014) noted that the State and Federal Universities in Nigeria are composed of members of Governing Council, Vice-Chancellors, Principals officers, Administrators (Deans and Heads of Departments (HODs), academic and non-academic staff. The administrators control the daily activities of academic and non-academic. The university administrators inform and clarify members of staff of their job responsibilities and expectations through communication.

Communication is the act of disseminating information, passing message and expressing feelings among two or persons. According to Akarika, Umoren and Okon (2021), communication is an expression of thoughts, feelings, ideas and messages from the sender to the receiver through verbal, non-verbal, written and non-written forms. It is a process by which individuals exchange information, share ideas, provide facts, express their thoughts, feelings and values in a given

setting. University administrators disseminate information and influence the activities of members of staff through different communication patterns.

Communication patterns are the channels and strategies employed by workforce of an organization in passing messages, sharing ideas and feelings among each other. According to Weldeghebiel, Mberia and Ndavula (2019), communication patterns deal with how information flows for smooth and better functioning of an organization. Communication patterns are techniques for creating, sending, and receiving information in the workplace. Fiel-Miranda and Miranda (2019) defined communication patterns as the ways of transmitting ideas, facts, thoughts, feelings and values between two or more persons. It is the structure in which information flow in an organization. Contextually, communication patterns are the sets of lines or flows of information by words, writing, symbols, body languages and other mediums. Several scholars identified communication pattern as follow: upward, downward and horizontal patterns (Badau, 2018; Joda, 2022, Akarika, Umoren and Okon, 2022; Uwandu, Udo-Anyanwu and Okorie, 2022). The focus of the study is on downward and horizontal patterns of communication.

Downward communication pattern is the flow of information from superiors to subordinates in an organization. Job descriptions, policies and goals of an organization are made known to subordinates through downward communication pattern. Ogunola and Akporaro (2015) asserted that when managers, supervisors, and team leaders communicate with the employees that are directly under them, downward communication is used. Continuing, they stressed that it is used to assign goals, provide job instructions, inform employees of policies and procedures, point out problems that need attention, and offer feedback about performance. The administrators who send letters to lecturers to informing them of deadline for lectures delivery and commencement of examinations have applied downward communication pattern. Badau (2018) pointed out that university leaders, from central office administrators to building-level administrators, communicate downward to members of academic and non-academic staff through speeches, messages in University bulletins, University board policy manuals, and school procedure handbooks. They added that the types of messages transmitted through downward pattern of communication are job instructions, job rationales and practices information, feedback and indoctrination. Some of the information communicated downward could be discussed and disseminated among staff of the same level through horizontal communication pattern.

Horizontal communication pattern is the style of exchanging information among members of staff across the same level or rank in an organization. Joda (2022) noted that horizontal communication is the transmission of information between people, divisions, departments or units within the same level of organizational hierarchy. Horizontal communication pattern helps to improve coordination between departments in the university. Badau (2018) noted that information disseminated through horizontal communication pattern is basically for coordination to tie together activities within or across departments on a single school campus or within divisions in a school-

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wide organisational system. Horizontal communication pattern takes place, when there is exchange of information among Heads of Departments, Divisional Heads and Unit Heads among others. Hee, Qin, Kowang, Husin and Ping (2019) asserted that horizontal communication pattern is useful in coordinating the activities of different departments in an organization. They added that it contributes in developing stronger relationship among staff in both similar department and different departments in an organization. The flow of information in universities could be enhanced by the leadership style of administrators.

Leadership styles are strategies adopted by administrators to influence and control the efforts of staff towards attainment of set goals and objectives. Leadership styles are series of approaches adopted by management towards ensuring members of staff diligently execute their duties. Dzakpasu, Amankwah, Konin and Amanfo (2022) defined leadership styles as the patterns of the manager's interaction or behaviour in guiding, structuring and facilitating activities and relationships in a school. Leadership styles are the behavioural patterns of operating the activities of an organization and influencing the efforts of members of staff to attain common goals. Narad, Kaitano and Lakhanpal (2020) defined leadership styles as the behavioural patterns that a leader adopt to influence and motivate the attitude of the followers to accomplish given objectives. Leadership styles are the peculiar ways of influencing the conduct of staff in the workplace. Operationally, leadership styles are the ways and approaches in which administrators provides direction, control and influence the activities of staff toward realising predetermined objectives. The leadership styles could inspire, demoralize or encourage the contribution of subordinates towards the attainment of set goals. Several scholars have outlined leadership styles as follows: democratic, autocratic and laissez-faires (Jidefor, 2022; Mohammad, Alam, Amin and Alam, 2019). This study focused on three leadership styles namely democratic, autocratic and laissez-faires because they influence the behaviour of staff in an organization.

The democratic leadership style is an approach of leading by participation and collaboration of subordinates. The university administrators who apply democratic leadership style seek the opinions of the subordinates before taking decisions on the affairs of the institutions. Achimugu and Obaka (2020) posited that the suggestions, recommendations, opinions and views of the subordinates who are affected by decisions are actively sought by administrators who apply democratic leadership style. They further asserted that democratic leaders encourage staff and students to participate actively, thereby making them feel engaged and motivated to attain predetermined goals and objectives of the institution. The democratic style of leadership encourages use of initiatives and promotes creativity as the inputs of lecturers are highly valued. Okoroma and Agbo (2022) posited that democratic leadership style encourages trust, promotes team work and cooperation among employees. They added that this leadership style makes workers to be motivated to do more as they are usually part of the entire process of reaching decision. The administrators who adopt democratic leadership style tend to treat members of staff

with kindness, respect and fairness. The administrators who use threats to get things done have applied autocratic leadership style,

Autocratic leadership style is characterised by the use punishment, threat, rules and regulations to guide the conduct of staff in an organization. Ziduli, Molepo, Buka and Jadezweni (2018) pointed out that autocratic leaders do not consult members of the organization in the decision-making process; they set all policies, predetermine the methods of work, determine the duties of followers, specify technical and performance evaluation standards. Autocratic administrators dictate all activities and work procedures in an organization. Jideofor (2022) asserted that autocratic leadership style is a self-centred leadership approach in which the superiors provide clear expectations of what needs to be done, when it should be done and how it should be done. Administrators who adopt autocratic style of leadership issue orders and give directives that must be obeyed by subordinates without any question. Achimugu and Obaka (2020) averred that autocratic style of leadership often engenders anger, frustration, despair, and in extreme cases withdrawal from school activities. Under autocratic style of leadership, there is limited freedom because of the domineering control by the administrators. Autocratic leadership style of administrators is likely to shape organizational climate of the university.

Organizational climate is the perception of the staff about the norms, practices and expectations in the work environment. Ezinine and Ughamadu (2021) defined organizational climate as the behavioural pattern, structure, norms, values, and traditions of a college that distinguish it from other organizations. Organizational climate is the shared beliefs and values that guide the work behaviour of staff of an establishment. According to Bello and Oredein (2022), organizational climate is the norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching, learning, management practices and structure of a workplace. Organizational climate is a set of characteristics, feelings and work norms which is created from the way an organization deals with its members. Operationally, organizational climate is core sets of norms, shared values and perceptions that influence the thoughts and actions of staff in the workplace.

The rapid demand for university education without corresponding leadership styles and communication patterns to build a favourable organizational climate creates the problem of institutional effectiveness in Nigeria. Some university administrators tend to disengage members of staff from making suggestions regarding tasks to be done for attainment of set organizational goals. This is buttressed by the observation of Ndukwe, Ukeje and Onele (2016) which indicated that some university administrators apply undemocratic leadership style by not only denying members of staff the opportunity to participate in decision/policy making but force them to complete tasks against their wish. They added that this has created organization climate of disloyalty and distrust which tend to leads to formation of coalitions and cliques among staff in public universities in South East, Nigeria. Some administrators tend to be too harsh to staff and

also demonstrate strictness by insisting on total compliance to lay down rules and procedures in public universities in South East, Nigeria.

There tends to be gap in the flow of information from the top-down and the bottom-up as it appears that communication from bottom-up is considered relevant only when problematic situation arises in public universities in South East, Nigeria. Badau (2018) observed that some administrators fail to respond when staff members bring up information or problems in Nigeria Universities. The author further noted that failure of university administrators to respond to request of members of staff will ultimately result in communication gaps. The communication gaps tends to make subordinates feel under-valued and left out in the affairs of universities which breed gossips, rumours and distrust that create unhealthy organizational climate. Nebo, Nwankwo and Okonkwo (2015) noted that the constant delay in accessing information by staff of universities in South East, Nigeria seems to create unfavourable organizational climate. This background prompted the investigation into communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The hostile, unsupportive and unhealthy atmosphere of some public universities in South East is probably due to untimely dissemination of information, closed-minded leadership behaviours of the university administrators and their leadership styles of ignoring of staff's suggestions on crucial matters which breed misunderstanding and confrontation. Inputs of some lecturers that tend to be sought during decision-making process appear to be hardly taken into considerations before deciding on university affairs in South East, Nigeria. Communication channels put by in place by some administrators tend to distract, interrupt and impede the flow of information from bottom-up in public universities in South East, Nigeria. Some administrators seem to be bossy, harsh and rely on the use threats to get work done by subordinates.

The hostile nature of some universities atmosphere in South East, Nigeria may be connected to communication gaps and rigid leadership behaviour of university administrators. The communication gaps could be associated with rumours and confusion in universities in South East, Nigeria. Some lecturers who are not well communicated about their roles by administrators are more likely to misunderstand their job requirements and expectations which undermine the success of the universities. The negative reactions of lecturers to the breakdown in communication in some universities in South East have somehow been reflecting in their absenteeism, low team spirit, grudges and poor interpersonal relationship with administrators. This prompted this study to investigate communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in south-east universities.

Purpose of the Study

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The study determined the communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria. Specifically, it determined

1. Downward communication pattern of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, Universities.
2. Horizontal communication pattern of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, Universities.
3. Democratic leadership style of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, Universities.
4. Autocratic leadership style of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, universities.
5. Communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between downward communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities?
2. What is the relationship between horizontal communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities?
3. What is the relationship between democratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities?
4. What is the relationship between autocratic leadership style of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, universities?
5. What is the relationship between communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between downward communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.
2. There is no significant relationship between horizontal communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.
3. There is no significant relationship between democratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.
4. There is no significant relationship between autocratic leadership style of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, universities.

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5. There is no significant relationship between communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria.

Methods

Correlation research design was adopted for this study. According to Nworgu (2015), this type of study seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. This design is appropriate since the study sought to collect data from respondents in order to investigate communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators as correlates of organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria. The study was conducted in South East, Nigeria which is bounded in the east by Benue and Cross River States, in the west by Delta State, in the North by Kogi State and in the South by Akwa Ibom and Rivers States. South East Nigeria has five states namely; Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo States.

The population of the study comprised 749 administrators in public universities in South East, Nigeria. The sample for the study comprised 300 administrators drawn using proportionate stratified sampling technique. The sample size was 40% of the population of the study.

Three sets of instruments titled Communication Patterns Questionnaire (CPQ), Leadership Styles Questionnaire (LSQ) and Organizational Climate Scale (QCS) were used to collect data. The first instrument titled CPQ was developed by the researcher from literature review and consultation of experts in the field of education. The instrument which measured communication patterns contains 14 items spread two clusters (1-2). Cluster 1 contained 7 items on downward communication pattern and Cluster 2 contained 7 items on horizontal communication pattern. The second instrument titled LSQ was developed by the researcher from literature review and consultation of experts in the field of education. The instrument which measured leadership styles contained 19 items spread three clusters (I-II). Cluster I contained 10 items on democratic leadership style and Cluster II contained 9 items on autocratic leadership style. The third instrument titled OCS was adopted from Pena-Suarez, Muniz, Campillo-Alvarez, Fonseca-Pedrero and Garcia-Cueto (2013). The instrument contained 25 items which measured organizational culture. The items of the three sets of instruments are placed on a 4-point rating of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts, two in the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The researcher presented the title, purpose of the study, research questions and hypotheses with a copy of the questionnaires to the three experts and requested them to examine and scrutinize the items in terms of relevance, suitability, clarity of instruction and content coverage. The experts suggested among others that leading statements should be provided in all

clusters and some items should be restructured. Their suggestions were used to produce the final version of the instrument. The reliability of the instruments were ascertained through Cronbach alpha. The internal consistency coefficient values of 0.81 and 0.79 were obtained for Cluster 1 and 2 of CPQ with overall reliability coefficient value of 0.80. On the other hand, the internal consistency coefficient values of 0.84 and 0.80 were obtained for Cluster I and II of LSQ with overall reliability coefficient value of 0.82, while the coefficient obtained for OCS was 0.82.

The researcher with the help of four research assistants who are lecturers in public universities in South East administered copies of the questionnaires to the respondents through a direct approach. A total of 300 copies of the questionnaires were distributed and 291 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 97% return rate. The copies of the questionnaires distributed, duly filled and successfully retrieved were used for data analysis. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions 1-6, t-test of correlation to test the hypotheses 1-8 and multiple regression to answer research question 9 and test hypothesis 9. For decision on the research questions, the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient by Alsagr (2021), as follows

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .19	Weak correlation
.20- .39	Fair correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of .05 the null hypotheses was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between downward communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities?

Variables	N	Downward Communication Pattern	Organizational Climate	Remarks
Downward Communication Pattern	291	1.00	.759	Strong Positive

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	Relationship		
Organizational Climate	291	.759	1.00

Table 1: Pearson (r) on Relationship Downward Communication Pattern of Administrators and Organizational Climate

Result in Table 1 revealed that Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) of .759 was obtained. This showed that there is strong positive relationship between downward communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This indicated that an improvement in downward communication pattern of administrators will contribute to positive organizational climate.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between horizontal communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities?

Table 2: Pearson (r) on Relationship Horizontal Communication Pattern of Administrators and Organizational Climate

Variables	N	Horizontal Communication Pattern	Organizational Climate	Remarks
Horizontal Communication Pattern	291	1.00	.715	Strong Positive Relationship
Organizational Climate	291	.715	1.00	

Table 2 indicated that a Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) of .715 was obtained. This showed that there is strong positive relationship between horizontal communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This indicated that increase in horizontal communication pattern of administrators will lead to better organizational climate.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between democratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities?

Table 3: Pearson (r) on Relationship Democratic Leadership Style of Administrators and Organizational Climate

Variables	N	Democratic Leadership Style	Organizational Climate	Remarks
Democratic Leadership Style	291	1.00	.818	Strong Positive Relationship
Organizational Climate	291	.818	1.00	

As shown in Table 3, Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of .818 was obtained. This showed that there is strong positive relationship between democratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This indicated that improvement on the democratic leadership style of administrators will contribute to better organizational climate.

Research Question 4: What is the relationship between autocratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities?

Table 4: Pearson (r) on Relationship Autocratic Leadership Style of Administrators and Organizational Climate

Variables	N	Autocratic Leadership Style	Organizational Climate	Remarks
Autocratic Leadership Style	291	1.00	.309	Fair Positive Relationship
Organizational Climate	291	.309	1.00	

Table 4 indicated that a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of .309 was obtained. This showed that there is fair positive relationship between autocratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This indicated that autocratic leadership style of administrators will contribute to fair organizational climate.

Research Question 5: What is the relationship between communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria?

Table 5: The Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis on Communication Patterns and Leadership Styles of Administrators as Correlates of Organizational Culture

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
1	.876	.767	.762	.283658	Strong

Table 5 showed that correlation coefficient of simple regression analysis is .876 with a coefficient of determination of .767. This shows that 76.7% variation in organizational Climate can be attributed to communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators. The regression Coefficient r of .876 indicated that there is strong positive relationship between communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between downward communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.

Table 6: The Summary of t-test of Correlation on the Significant Relationship between Downward Communication Pattern of Administrators and Organizational Climate

Variables	N	Downward Communication Pattern	Organizational Climate	P -Value	∞	Remark
Downward Communication Pattern	291	1	.759	.000	.05	Rejected
Organizational Climate	291	.759	1			

Table 6 revealed that the p -value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is

significant relationship between downward communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between horizontal communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.

Table 7: The Summary of t-test of Correlation on the Significant Relationship between Horizontal Communication Pattern of Administrators and Organizational Climate

Variables	N	Horizontal Communication Pattern	Organizational Climate	<i>P-Value</i>	∞	Remark
Horizontal Communication Pattern	291	1	.715	.000	.05	Rejected
Organizational Climate	291	.715	1			

The result presented in Table 7 revealed that the *p*-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the *p*-value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between horizontal communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between democratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.

Table 8: The Summary of t-test of Correlation on the Significant Relationship between Democratic Leadership Style of Administrators and Organizational Climate

Variables	N	Democratic Leadership Pattern	Organizational Climate	<i>P-Value</i>	∞	Remark
Democratic Leadership Style	291	1	.818	.000	.05	Rejected
Organizational Climate	291	.818	1			

The result presented in Table 8 revealed that the *p*-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the *p*-value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected.

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Therefore, there is significant relationship between democratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between autocratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.

Table 9: The Summary of t-test of Correlation on the Significant Relationship between Autocratic Leadership Style of Administrators and Organizational Climate

Variables	N	Autocratic Leadership Pattern	Organizational Climate	<i>P-Value</i>	∞	Remark
Autocratic Leadership Style	291	1	.309	.000	.05	Rejected
Organizational Climate	291	.309	1			

Table 9 showed that the *p*-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the *p*-value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between autocratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant relationship between communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria.

Table 10: The Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis on Communication Patterns and Leadership Styles of Administrators as Correlates of Organizational Climate

Predictor	R	R ²	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	Remark
Communication Patterns and Leadership Styles	.876	.767	158.856	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 10, the multiple regression coefficient (R) is .876 while the R² is .767 showing that communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators make 76.7% contribution to the variance organizational climate. The *F* (1/291) =158.556 and the *p*-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the *p*-value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria.

Discussion

The result of the study indicated that there is strong positive relationship between downward communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This is in conformity with the finding of Thet and Htarr (2020) which indicated that there was positively strong relationship between principals' downward communication pattern and school climate. The agreement in findings could be associated with the fact that the two studies were conducted in educational institutions where administrators give instructions and provide directions using downward communication pattern. This is in disagreement with the finding of This contradicted the finding of Sopian, Abdullah, Ghani, Abdullah and Omar (2019) which indicated that there was moderate relationship between principals' downward communication pattern and school climate. The difference in geographical locations where there are different policies guiding downward communication pattern. This finding is explained by the fact that downward communication pattern is a means of providing instructions and disseminating information on policies, rules and work procedures enable subordinate become aware of their job roles and expected behaviour contribute to strong organizational climate. Downward communication pattern is strongly correlated with organizational climate due to the fact that it helps to keep members of staff up-dated and well-informed of tasks to be done and how to execute the tasks. The university administrators through downward communication pattern delegate duties and instill a sense of responsibilities to subordinates which contribute ton strong organizational climate.

Further result indicated that there is significant relationship between downward communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This is in line with the finding of Thet and Htarr (2020) which revealed that there was significant relationship between principals' downward communication pattern and school climate. The university administrators give order and directives to the subordinates through downward communication pattern to ensure uniformity and compliance to standard mode of operations which explain the significant relationship with organizational climate. The mission and values of universities shared with members of staff through downward communication pattern enable them understand the expected attitude towards achieving the values which thereby create favourable organizational climate.

It was revealed that indicated that there is strong positive relationship between horizontal communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This is in agreement with the finding of Lannes (2021) which showed a strong positive correlation between organizational horizontal communication and organizational climate. Horizontal communication pattern which ensures unity of purpose among departments or teams at the same level in universities could explain the strong relationship with organizational culture. Members of staff with the same job title could work together to achieve interdependent goals through horizontal communication pattern. Some departments who are dependent on one another for vital information

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in executing tasks could create strong organizational climate through horizontal communication pattern. The opportunity in which horizontal communication pattern provides for staff at the same level to communicate directly without going through the university administrators could account for the strong relationship with organizational climate.

Further finding showed that there is significant relationship between horizontal communication pattern of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This affirmed the finding of Sidiropoulou (2021) which showed a significant correlation between organizational horizontal communication and organizational climate. Horizontal communication pattern which facilitates information sharing and task coordination between departments or units could account for the significant relationship with organizational climate.

The finding of the study indicated that there is strong positive relationship between democratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This supported the finding of Zamin and Hussin (2021) which showed there was a strong positive relationship between democratic leadership style and work climate. This is also in line with the finding of Barnova, Trelova, Krasna, Benova, Hasajova and Gabrhelova (2022) which indicated democratic leadership style has strong correlation with school climate. The agreement in the findings of the studies could be connected to the fact that the two studies were conducted in educational institutions. This finding is probably due to the fact that democratic leadership style which empowers subordinates to participate in decision-making process could make them feel valued and thereby create strong and healthy organizational climate. Open discussion and sharing of new idea encouraged by administrators who apply democratic leadership style lead to feeling of trust, loyalty and team cohesion could be connected with the strong relationship with organizational climate. Members of staff feel more involved, committed and inspired to take action that foster healthy organizational climate through their inputs and ideas solicited by democratic administrators.

Further result showed that there is significant relationship between democratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This is in consonance with the finding of Barnova, Trelova, Krasna, Benova, Hasajova and Gabrhelova (2022) which showed democratic leadership style has significant correlation with school climate. University administrators who apply democratic style inspire trust and respect among subordinates which could account for the significant relationship with organizational climate. University administrators who apply democratic leadership style delegate responsibilities, foster participatory management and team work which help to build strong organizational climate.

The result of the study indicated that there is fair positive relationship between autocratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This agreed with the finding of Zamin and Hussin (2021) which revealed that there was a fair positive and significant relationship between autocratic leadership style and work culture. This disagreed with the finding of Philip, Ibrahim and Yussof (2020) which revealed that there exist weak

relationship between autocratic leadership style and organizational climate. The difference in geographical location could explain the disagreement in findings. The autocratic administrators who deprive subordinates the opportunities to make inputs and provide feedback on the affairs of university lead to feeling of mistrust and this breeds misunderstanding which could explain the fair relationship with organizational climate. The absolute control over subordinates by administrators who apply autocratic leadership impair creative ideas and inputs that tend to lead to physical confrontation which could contribute to the fair relationship with organizational climate. Autocratic administrators fail to value the suggestions of subordinates decrease their morale and create unfair organizational climate.

Further finding showed that there is significant relationship between autocratic leadership style of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities. This refuted the finding of Philip, Ibrahim and Yussof (2020) which showed that there was no significant relationship between autocratic leadership style and organizational climate. This disagreed with the finding of Ngoma, Sakakombe and Kabeta (2019) which indicated that the relationship between autocratic leadership style and school climate was not statistically significant. This disagreement could be attributed to the fact that the studies were conducted in different levels of education where the school administrators have different qualifications and experience that guide their use of autocratic leadership style to shape the school climate.

It was showed that there is strong positive relationship between communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria. This supported the finding of Witarini and Sriathi (2020) which showed that there is joint strong relationship between leadership styles, effective communication and organizational climate. This finding is explained by the fact that communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators determine the social norms, values and expected behaviour that forms the organizational climate of universities. The interaction of administrators with subordinates, decision-making process as well as work procedures which are instrumental in creating strong organizational climate is determined by the communication patterns and leadership styles in universities.

Further result showed that there is significant relationship between communication patterns, leadership styles of administrators and organizational climate in South East, Universities, Nigeria. This agreed with the finding of Witarini and Sriathi (2020) which showed that there is significant relationship between leadership styles, effective communication and organizational climate. This finding is explained by the fact that the flow of information determined by communication patterns of administrators as well as their leadership styles which influence the work behaviour of staff could significantly create the organizational climate of universities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that the communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators have positive and significant relationship with organizational climate in South East, Universities. Communication patterns and leadership styles of administrators help to convey information about core values, mission and expected behaviour that create organizational culture of universities. It is the patterns of communication and styles of leadership that could inspire open discussion, good interpersonal relationship, teamwork and honest feedback that strongly shape the organizational culture of universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. University management should formulate programme and modalities that encourage downward communication pattern by creating innovative channels for timely dissemination of information to members of staff and students for healthy organizational climate.
2. University council should create flowchart that provide details of communication between departments or units with regard to frequency and mode of communication which will foster horizontal communication pattern and strongly improve organizational climate.
3. University administrators should practice democratic leadership style by encouraging open communication and friendly environment that embolden subordinates to express how they think and feel things could be done to strongly create healthy organizational climate.
4. University administrators should modify their autocratic leadership style by considering the inputs of subordinates in operation of daily affairs to create positive organizational climate.
5. University management should organize training programmes in forms of annually or quarterly conferences, seminars, short-courses and workshops to enable administrators acquire skills and knowledge of applying communication patterns and leadership styles to create positive organizational climate.

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